

each about 3 μ long. The sex-determining mechanism was XX-XO type, the male being heterogametic and the female

homogametic. Thus, the complete genome in males comprised 14 bivalent autosomes plus an X chromosome

(Fig. 2), whereas females had 14 bivalent autosomes plus XX sex chromosomes. □

A *Leersia*-feeding brown planthopper (BPH) biotype in North Sumatra, Indonesia

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We found a large BPH population of macropterous and brachypterous adults and nymphs at various instars inhabiting *Leersia hexandra* in a fallow rice field at Petapahan, Lubuk Pakam, Deli Serdang, North Sumatra, in Sep 1983. Except for significantly smaller body size, morphological characters of BPH specimens collected on *L. hexandra* and on IR42 and Pelita I/1 at the same location were identical (Fig. 1).

Preliminary experiments compared the reactions of *Leersia*-BPH to host plants with the reaction of BPH biotype 3 which infests rice in North Sumatra. In a host preference test in a cage with *L. hexandra* and susceptible Pelita I/1, adult females of *Leersia*-BPH all settled on *L. hexandra* within 1 d, while biotype 3 females rejected it. Adult females of *Leersia*-BPH survived only a few days and reproduced little progeny on Pelita I/1. They survived

1. Paramere of the *Leersia*-BPH(upper) and rice feeding BPH, biotype 3 (lower).

normally and reproduced readily on *L. hexandra*. One *Leersia*-BPH female allowed to oviposit on *L. hexandra* for 1 wk produced about 120 nymphs. When the first-instar nymphs were

2. Survival trends of *Leersia*-BPH and biotype 3 nymphs on detached *L. hexandra*.

reared on detached stems of *L. hexandra* in test tubes, 93-100% of nymphs emerged to adults within 2 wk. First-instar biotype 3 nymphs died (Fig. 2). Female *Leersia*-BPH excreted little honeydew on Pelita I/1 and IR42 (2-4 mg/female daily). Biotype 3 females excreted 30-40 mg honeydew/female daily.

These results indicate that the *Leersia*-BPH is a distinct host-determined BPH biotype. □

Hot water treatment to remove insects from rice plants used in the plant-hopper and leafhopper rearing program

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In the IRRI GEU program, thousands of rice plants are grown each month as food for the hopper rearing program. Because greenhouse space is limited they must be grown outdoors, where they are often infested with eggs of the various hopper species and predators. This contamination leads to

mixing of hopper biotypes and brings unwanted predators into the rearing cages. To eliminate those insects, plants are sprayed with water and placed in cages. Hatching nymphs are removed after 11 d. This is time-consuming and requires greenhouse space.

We evaluated hot water treatment for control of brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*, whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera*, green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*, and the predatory mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*.

Gravid females of BPH, WBPH, GLH, and *Cyrtorhinus* were separately

Egg mortality caused by dipping rice plants in 44°C hot water for 30 min. Bars with different letters differ significantly at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.